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Exploring the Nexus between Terrorism and Environmental Degradation: A South Asian Perspective

Khyzran

Department of Economics Kohat University of Science & Technology (KUST), Kohat, Pakistan Email: khiz.ali51214@gmail.com

Alam Khan (Corresponding Author)

Department of Economics Kohat University of Science & Technology (KUST), Kohat, Pakistan Email: alamkhan@kust.edu.pk

Dilawar Khan

Department of Economics Kohat University of Science & Technology (KUST), Kohat, Pakistan Email: dilawar@kust.edu.pk

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ABSTRACT

This research investigated the relationship between terrorism and environmental degradation in South Asia employing a balanced panel data approach covering the period from 2003-2021 for Bangladesh, India, Nepal, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka. A critical examination of existing literature reveals the positive link between terrorism and environmental degradation in South Asian nations. The study utilized panel unit root tests, panel cointegration test and panel ARDL. Variables such as CO₂ emissions, terrorism index, GDP per capita, urban population, foreign direct investment, and climate change index found to have mix order of integration with I(0) and I(1). The research conducted econometric tools like Panel ARDL to capture the short and long run dynamics. In the long run, the gross domestic product per capita (GDP) shows a non-linear relationship with environmental degradation, where the first term (LGDP1) has a positive and significant impact (coefficient = 0.22984, p-value = 0.0226). The Climate Change Index (DLCCI) continues to have a positive and significant effect on CO₂ emissions in the short run (coefficient = 0.357511, p-value = 0.0108). Ultimately, this research seeks to offer valuable insights for policymakers, humanitarian organizations, and environmental security measures.

Key Words: Environmental Degradation; Terrorism; ARDL; South Asia.

Introduction

Terrorism is a field of study that is endogenous in nature and mutually intersects with politics, sociology, psychology, economics, and international relations. In fact, as noted by Klein (2007) and Teitler-Regev & Tavor (2019), terrorist organizations aim to create psychological, social, political, and financial harm in addition to the deaths and material destruction they produce. In addition to killing tens of thousands of people worldwide, they also have a negative direct and indirect impact on the environment and socioeconomics. Kunreuther et al. (2003) defines terrorism as the deliberate use of violence or the threat of violence by individuals or subnational groups to achieve a political or social goal by intimidating a sizable audience beyond the immediate victim.

Another biggest problem of the world is environmental degradation, which also has a direct or indirect impact on local climatic conditions by altering precipitation and temperature patterns (Fedorowicz-Kruszewska, 2023). Arctic ice melts more quickly as global temperatures rise, raising the sea level as a result (Sharma et al. 2022). For analyzing environmental performance, the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) is one of the most widely used techniques based on an inverted U-shaped curve developed by Kuznets in 1955. According to (EKC) theory, environmental degradation initially rises as a nation's economy expands but eventually declines as wealth and technology keep rising. The EKC is shaped like an inverted U, with environmental deterioration rising at first and then declining as a nation's wealth increases (Maneejuk et al., 2020).

Environmental deterioration and terrorism have recently been linked to terrorism. Terrorism has become more common, with severe effects on the environment, the economy, human life and habitats found in nature. According to Tahir et al. (2022), terrorism poses a significant threat to environmental sustainability and can have detrimental effects on society's socioeconomic levels over an extended period. According to Bildirici and Gokmenoglu (2020), terrorism and terrorist attacks intensify the emissions of hazardous gases, which have an immediate impact on the quality of the environment. Massively harmful substances like carbon dioxide (CO₂)

and sulfur dioxide (SO₂) are produced by terrorist acts like bomb blasts, and these pollutants directly harm the ecosystem by depleting natural resources (Mannion 2003). Terrorism poses a significant threat to environmental sustainability and can have detrimental effects on society's socioeconomic levels over an extended period (Tahir et al. 2022).

Many studies have investigated the effect of terrorism on environment, with the majority concentrating on the immediate effects of terrorism on air and water quality. For instance, a study discovered that terrorist acts in Nigeria significantly worsened air quality by raising the quantity of particulate matter and nitrogen dioxide. Zhang et al., (2019) discovered that terrorist strikes in China caused a brief spike in air pollution, which had a detrimental effect on people's health. Similarly, Crawford (2019) revealed that the war on terror is responsible for contributing 35% of CO₂ emissions in the 21st century.

Assessing the impact of terrorism on environmental degradation is important for several reasons. First terrorist activities can directly contribute to environmental degradation through actions such as bombings, sabotage, or deliberate pollution. Second, terrorist organizations often rely on illicit activities to fund their operations, such as illegal logging, poaching, or smuggling of natural resources. Third terrorism can indirectly contribute to environmental degradation by targeting infrastructure related to energy production or transportation. In this work, we seek to identify and examine the impact of terrorism on environmental degradation in South Asia. Previous studies have investigated the influence of different variables on climate change, but none of studies examined the influence of terrorism on environmental degradation. This is the first study to investigate the impact of terrorism on environmental degradation for five South Asian countries using balanced panel data.

In this study, three indicators (incidence, fatality, and injuries of terrorist acts) were used to construct a terrorism index by a principal component analysis (PCA). Therefore, this study will bring an addition to the existing stock of literature about environmental degradation and its determinants.

The study proceeds as follows: section 2 reviews previous research studies related to this study. The third section explains the whole methodology used in this study. The fourth section presents the results and discussion of this study in detail. The final section presents the concluding remarks and outlines the policy measures regarding climate change mitigation.

Literature Review.

León et al. (2014) used the STIRPAT analytical methodology on a sample size of panels from industrialized and emerging economies and came to the conclusion that tourism affects carbon emissions in data panels. However, they also stated that the tourism industry's consumption and production stages contribute to a higher proportion of carbon emissions in developed economies. Katircioglu (2014) proposes a long-term relationship between tourism, economic growth, and environmental quality. Specifically, tourism raises energy consumption in Turkey, which boosts economic development but also degrades the environment. Zaman et al. (2016) supports the link between tourism and carbon emissions using sample size of industrialized and emerging economies and suggests that energy consumption and economic development are other factors that contribute to increased carbon emissions. Furthermore, advancements in health care, investments, and economic growth all contribute to the promotion of tourism. Sageman (2014) explained that along with all impacted nations the international community will need to take proactive and

coordinated actions to counter the threats that terrorism poses to ecological, human, and peace security. According to Mccauley and Moskalenko (2017), the quick proliferation of violence related to terrorism on social media can be attributed to the rise of ISIL as an international terrorist network from the Middle East. According to Bandyopadhyay et al. (2018), violence destroys a nation's financial system and undermines investor and consumer trust. It also costs enormous sums of money for infrastructure and communication. This makes it more difficult for a nation to change its production curve, which has a negative impact on GDP. Thus, the amount of financial effect depends on how frequently terrorist operations occur in a certain area. Okafor and Piesse (2018) empirically investigated the determinants of terrorism from fragile states. Their study concluded that Terrorism is positive and significantly impacted by number of refugees and youth unemployment. Military spending was found to be positive but less robust across models.

Bildirici and Gokmenoglu (2020) examined the impact of terrorism and FDI on environmental pollution. The panel cointegration results revealed that environmental pollution is the result of significant effect of terrorism, FDI, economic growth and energy consumption. A bi-directional causality between CO₂ emissions and other variables of the study was detected in the long run.

Chisti et. al (2021) examined a linear and non-linear impact of terrorism and FDI on carbon dioxide emission for ten most impacted countries because of terrorism. The results showed that there is a dominant negative impact on the environment from positive shocks to terrorism and foreign direct investment inflows suggesting that the sample economies should encourage public awareness, promote education in order to alleviate terrorism. To lessen the negative environmental effects of FDI strict environmental rules on foreign direct investment inflows are also necessary. 35 percent of the 21st century's CO₂ emissions can be attributed to the fight on terror (Crawford, 2019). Gao et al. (2022) examine the relationship between environmental, FDI and terrorism across different countries. The study concluded that terrorism and environment have a positive link.

Tahir et al. (2022) investigated that effect of terrorism on environmental sustainability in the case of Middle East and north Africa (MENA). The study found that terrorism generates environmental degradation. Kilic et al. (2024) in their study for 17 countries with most terrorism antecedents explores association between environmental degradation, foreign direct investment and terrorism. According to their findings terrorism does not possess any significant influence on ecological footprint while foreign direct investment does.

Methodology

This study aims to investigate the impact of terrorism on environmental degradation for five South Asian countries for the time period 2000 to 2021 based on panel data. The study faced unavailability of data for countries like Maldives, Bhutan and Afghanistan was missing so these countries were not included in the study. In the study CO₂ emission will be used as the dependent variable for environmental degradation (ED), while terrorism T, Gross domestic product per capita (GDP), climate change (CCI), Foreign direct investment (FDI) and population (POP) will be used as independent variables. Sources used to extract data for dependent and independent variables which include World Bank and Global Terrorism Database 2024. The dependent variable CO₂ is measured in metric tons per capita, independent variables like GDP per capita is measured in constant US dollar 2015, population

represents urban population in million people, foreign direct index are the net inflows (percentage of GDP), Climate change and Terrorism are the index taken from global terrorism data base. The description of variables used in the study is given in table 1. The expression specified to estimate the effect of terrorism on environmental degradation is as below.

$$CO_2 = f(T, GDP, Pop, FDI, CCI) \quad (1)$$

In order to obtain more efficient and dependent estimation equation 1 is converted into log form. Equation 1 in log-log form is given as under.

$$\ln ED_{2it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln T + \beta_2 \ln GDP + \beta_3 \ln Pop + \beta_4 \ln FDI + \beta_5 \ln CCI + e_{it} \quad (2)$$

Where $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ represents the intercept and slope coefficients respectively, i denotes cross-sectional unit or country, t denotes the time period and e_{it} is the error term.

Table 1. Variables Description

Abbreviation	Description	Unit	Data Source
ED	Environmental degradation	CO2 emissions metric tons per capita	World Bank (2024)
T	Terrorism	Index	GTD (2024)
GDP	Gross domestic product per capita	GDP per capita 2015 US dollars	World Bank (2024)
Pop	Urban Population	Million	World Bank (2024)
FDI	Foreign direct investment	Net inflows (% GDP)	World Bank (2024)
CCI	Climate change index	Index	World bank (2024)

CO₂ emissions per capita are used in this study to quantify environmental degradation. The metric represents the average quantity of carbon dioxide emissions that a person in a nation produces. It acts as a vital indicator of the state of the environment and the ecological imprint of a certain area. Greater environmental deterioration is indicated by higher values, and this degradation can be caused by a number of reasons, such as industrial activity, energy usage, and policy decisions. Examining how economic activity and socio-political variables, such terrorism, may contribute to environmental harm in South Asia is made possible by concentration on CO₂ emissions.

Terrorism denotes the frequency and severity of terrorism in the area. The index in use is a composite metric that takes into consideration the incidence, fatality, and financial impact of terrorist acts. The Global Terrorism Database offers a quantitative way to evaluate the impact of terrorism by providing extensive data on terrorist incidents. This variable is essential to comprehending how much terrorism can influence environmental laws and practices, cause policy changes, or disturb socio-economic activities, all of which can contribute to environmental degradation.

A common economic metric used to determine a region's average economic output per person is GDP per capita. It is computed by dividing a nation's total GDP by its population, and in order to account for inflation, the result is expressed in constant 2015 US dollars. This variable aids in accounting for the economic standing of South

Asian nations and evaluating the relationship between environmental degradation and economic progress. The environmental Kuznets curve (EKC) proposes the inverted U-shaped relationship between environmental degradation (ED) and GDP. Environmental degradation starts increasing at the initial level stages of GDP growth and then it decreases at a higher level of economic growth. It offers a framework for comprehending the possible relationships between economic resources and environmental effects, such as reactions to terrorism.

The number of people living in urban regions, given in millions, is measured by the urban population variable. An analysis of the contribution of urbanization to environmental degradation requires this demographic indicator. Pollution and resource consumption are generally higher in urban settings, which can worsen environmental degradation. Comprehending the population distribution between urban and rural regions can offer valuable perspectives on the environmental stresses linked to urbanization, especially when considering the backdrop of economic growth and terrorism.

When represented as a percentage of GDP, FDI stands for net inflows of investment from foreign entities. This variable shows how much foreign investment and economic participation there is in the area. Depending on the type of investment, foreign direct investment (FDI) can have a good or negative impact on environmental deterioration. Investments in polluting sectors can raise emissions, whilst investments in environmentally friendly technologies can lower them. Given that political unrest has the potential to discourage foreign investors or change their investment patterns, the role of FDI is equally pertinent in the context of terrorism.

Climate Change Index, which is an aggregate indicator. This index is essential for evaluating the larger environmental framework within which socioeconomic issues and terrorism function. It aids in taking into consideration the outside factors, separate from terrorism, that could impact environmental deterioration. A more comprehensive understanding of the baseline environmental circumstances obtained from the CCI can help to clarify any extra effects that terrorism might have on environmental degradation.

It is necessary to check variables for their order of integration before estimating a relationship between environmental degradation and other independent variables. Most of the time the economic time series consists of non-stationarity or unit root problem. If regression is conducted on the non-stationary data, then it will be spurious regression giving misleading results. Unit root tests are employed to evaluate the stationarity of a time series. A fluctuation in a time series that is non-stationary results in an unaltered distribution structure; non-stationarity is caused by unit roots. Non-stationarity can be caused by a variety of factors, such as unit roots, temporal trends, and structural discontinuities. For examining the order of unit root, Levin Lin (LL) test and Lm Pesaran and shin (LPS) test are commonly used. The LL test is an extension of Dickey Fuller (DF) Test. LL test was originally proposed by Levin and Lin in 1992 and was published in 2002 with Chu as co-author (see Levin et al., 2002). The general model for this test can be written as follows.

$$\Delta Y_{i,t} = \alpha_i + \sigma Y_{i,t-1} + \sum_j^n \gamma Y_{i,t-j} + \phi_t + e_t \quad (3)$$

LL model allows for a two-way fixed effect and includes two terms. The first term α_i (unit specific fix effect) and the second one is ϕ_t (unit specific time effect). Since the coefficient (σ) of lagged Y_i is restricted to being homogenous across all units of panel ϕ_t allows for heterogeneity. The null and alternative hypotheses are formulated as

follows. $H_0; \varpi = 0$ (non stationary) $H_a; \varpi < 0$ (stationary). The Levin and Lin test assumes that the individual processes are cross-sectionally independent hence the test derives the conditions for which the pooled OLS estimator of σ will follow a standard normal distribution under the null hypotheses. The null hypothesis states that the data is non-stationary and stationary under the alternative hypotheses.

LL test may be considered to that of pooled ADF test having different lags varying with different sections in panel. The LM test devised by Lm et al (1997) covers the drawback of LL test by

- (a) allowing heterogeneity for the coefficient of $Y_{i,t-1}$, (b) Proposing basic testing procedure, the one based on mean value of individual unit root test. This test measures that T should be the same for all crosection. Their t-statistical value is the average value of individual ADF t-statistics for testing that $\sigma_i = 0$ for all i denoted by t_{pi}

$$t = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N t_{pi} \quad (4)$$

The general model for this model is given by

$$\Delta Y_{i,t} = \alpha_i + \sigma Y_{i,t-1} + \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_{ik} \Delta Y_{i,t-k} + \phi_{it} + u_{it} \quad (5)$$

The alternative and null hypotheses are as for all i $H_0; \sigma_i = 0$ (non-stationary) for at least one i $H_a; \sigma_i < 0$ (stationary).

After variables are checked for their order of integration the study conducted Panel Auto regressive Distributed Lagged Model PMG-ARDL to check the long-run and short-run relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Panel ARDL model can be used if all the variables have same order of integration i.e variables are integrated at level I(0) or at first difference I(1) or combination of both I(0), I(1) some at level and some stationary at first difference. PMG-ARDL solves endogeneity problem and makes the possible hypothesis which is based estimated long-run coefficients, difficult through the Engle-Granger approach. This model also estimates both short and long-run coefficients simultaneously (Pesaran et.al 1999).

To achieve the objective of this study the following, The general model of ARDL is given below:

$$\Delta \ln CO_{2\ i,t} = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \epsilon_{1i} \Delta \ln CO_{2\ t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \alpha_{1ij} \Delta \ln T_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \alpha_{2ij} \Delta \ln GDP_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \alpha_{3ij} \Delta \ln Pop_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \alpha_{4ij} \Delta \ln FDI_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \alpha_{5ij} \Delta CCI_{it-j} + \phi_{1i} ITO_{it} + \phi_{2i} GDP_{it-j} + \phi_{3i} Pop_{it-j} + \phi_{4i} FDI_{it-j} + \phi_{5i} CCI_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \epsilon_6 \Delta IECT_{it-j} + U_{ij} \quad (6)$$

From eq. 6 $\Delta \ln GDP_{i,t}$ Represents the first difference of GDP where as $\Delta \ln GDP_{i,t-1}$ represents the lag value of $\Delta \ln GDP_{i,t}$. $\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3, \phi_4, \phi_5$ represents the long-term coefficients. $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4, \alpha_5$ are the short run coefficients. ϕ Represent the error correction term and it is the speed of adjustment after disequilibrium from short-run to long-run.

$$Y_{i,t} = \alpha_i + \varpi Y_{i,t} + \beta_{1i} x_{1i,t} + \beta_{2i} x_{2i,t} + \beta_{jixji} + e_{i,t} \quad (7)$$

Where $t = 1, \dots, T; i = 1, \dots, N; j = 1, \dots, M$ and x is expected to be I(1). The factors α_i and ϖ_i are individual and drift effects, which may be fixed at zero if required. As mentioned above, if there is no co-integration, the residuals $e_{i,t}$ will be I(1). Generally, an auxiliary regression is run on the residuals obtained from above equation (7) and tested if I(1) for each cross-section.

$$e_{i,t} = \rho_i e_{i,t-1} + u_{it} \quad (8)$$

Results and discussion

Since the study's main objective was to determine how terrorism affects environmental deterioration in South Asia, time series data covering the years 2003 to 2021 were employed in the investigation. The chapter begins with descriptive statistics for the variables, followed by a test for stationarity to make sure the data is stationary, and lastly the application of a dynamic, panel ARDL approach to ascertain the co-integration between variables. Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study.

The mean values of ED for Bangladesh, India, Nepal, Pakistan and Srilanka are 0.392, 1.408, 0.267, 0.768, and 0.815 respectively. Similarly, the mean values of T for Bangladesh, India, Nepal, Pakistan and Srilanka are 1.684, 3.211, 1.685, 4.605, and 1.844 respectively. The mean values of GDP, Pop, FDI and CCI for Bangladesh, India, Nepal, Pakistan and Srilanka are 1116.42, 1390.17, 796.23, 1228.80, 3455.615 and 49362468, 405529.0, 4850.562, 71073.32, 3824.55 and 0.926, 1.768, 0.284, 1.209, 1.179 and 4.067, 2.183, 4.242, 4.334, 4.722 respectively. India has the highest mean value for environmental degradation (ED) while Nepal has the lowest mean value. The mean value of T was found to be highest for Pakistan and lowest in the case of Bangladesh. Mean value of GDP was highest in the case of Srilanka while lowest in the case of Nepal. Pakistan has the highest mean value in the case of Pop while lowest in the case of Srilanka. The average value of FDI was highest for India while it was lowest for Nepal. The mean value of CCI.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Variable	CO ₂	T	GDP	Pop	FDI	CCI
Bangladesh						
Mean	0.392	1.684	1116.421	49362468	0.926	4.067
Max	0.602	2.466	1684.434	65957486	1.735	5.380
Min	0.209	1.537	698.732	34711400	0.407	3.380
Std. Dev	0.132	0.209	310.541	9767859.	0.397	0.567
India						
Mean	1.408	3.211	1390.170	405529.0	1.768	2.183
Max	1.801	3.902	1941.815	498179.1	3.620	3.310
Min	0.905	2.539	840.817	319267.8	0.605	1.270
Std. Dev	0.302	0.356	373.203	55955.99	0.695	0.663
Nepal						
Mean	0.267	1.685	796.233	4850.562	0.284	4.242
Max	0.576	2.459	1061.486	6309.750	0.677	5.250
Min	0.098	1.533	570.419	3733.781	-0.073	3.500
Std. Dev	0.168	0.219	163.903	753.52	0.219	0.564
Pakistan						
Mean	0.768	4.605	1228.800	71073.32	1.209	4.334
Max	0.918	9.927	1473.865	86636.95	3.668	5.490
Min	0.633	1.780	985.653	56037.19	0.382	3.180
Std. Dev	0.073	2.267	147.539	9380.409	1.006	0.634
Sri Lanka						
Mean	0.815	1.844	3455.615	3824.557	1.179	4.722

Max	1.106	3.513	4495.711	4178.622	1.863	5.510
Min	0.600	1.523	2130.952	3539.045	0.410	4.150
Std. Dev	0.185	0.510	848.479	183.034	0.417	0.324

Table 3 shows that all other variables are stable at first difference, with the exception of Terrorism (T) and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), which are both stationary at level. The initial difference's integration order is shown by I(1), and the variable's stationarity at a level where its probability values are less than 0.05 is indicated by I(0).

The variables in the study are D (LCO₂), TI, D(LGDP1), D(LGDP2), D(LNFDI), and D(CCI), with "D" standing for the corresponding variable's initial difference. The approach utilized is the Im, Pesaran, and Shin W-stat test, a widely used method in panel data to look for unit roots in various series.

Table 3 Findings of Unit Root Test

Variable	At Level		At First Difference		
	Coefficient	Prob	Coefficient	Prob	Conclusion
CO ₂	1.089	0.138	5.111	0.016	I(1)
T	4.493	0.000	---	---	I(0)
GDP1	0.994	0.160	3.990	0.000	I(1)
GDP2	0.828	0.203	3.930	0.033	I(1)
Pop	0.284	0.388	5.782	0.028	I(1)
FDI	1.946	0.025	---	---	I(0)

After conducting unit root tests, the outcomes of an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model used to evaluate the short- and long-term effects of many variables, such as terrorism, on global environmental degradation in South Asia. The long-run equation and the short-run equation comprise the two components of the analysis.

Table 4. Findings of Panel ARDL

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Long Run Equation				
LGDP1	0.229	0.100	2.295	0.022
LGDP2	-0.741	0.276	-2.679	0.012
LFDI1	0.027	0.012	2.163	0.032
LCC1	0.900	0.378	2.378	0.021
LTP	0.049	0.021	2.270	0.025
LTEROR	0.016	0.006	2.498	0.018
Short Run Equation				
COINTEQ	-0.184	0.075	-2.440	0.019
DLGDP1	3.990	1.808	2.207	0.029
DLGDP2	-23.652	0.006	-2.398	0.020

DLFDI	-0.018	0.006	-3.032	0.012
DLCCI	0.357	0.126	2.836	0.010
DLTP	0.478	0.151	3.163	0.008
DLTEROR	0.143	0.066	2.175	0.041
C	0.174	2.108	0.082	0.034

The model presents predicted long- and short-term equations that provide light on the link between macroeconomic and socio-political issues, including terrorism, in South Asia and environmental degradation as assessed by CO₂ emissions.

In the long run there is a non-linear correlation between environmental degradation and GDP per capita. Specifically, the first term (LGDP1) has a significant and positive impact (p-value = 0.0226, coefficient = 0.22984), indicating that higher GDP initially causes more environmental degradation. The second term, GDP2, however, shows a negative effect (coefficient = -0.74158, p-value = 0.0128), suggesting that, as part of the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis, further increases in GDP per capita after a certain threshold help to reduce environmental degradation. This is probably because of improved technologies and environmental awareness.

Additionally, environmental degradation is positively and significantly impacted by foreign direct investment (LFDI1) (coefficient = 0.027149, p-value = 0.0324). This suggests that although FDI may promote economic growth, it may also have a negative impact on the environment, possibly as a result of laxer environmental regulations in South Asian nations. An unpleasant climate exacerbates environmental deterioration, as demonstrated by the Climate Change Index (LCC1), which has a strong positive influence on CO₂ emissions (coefficient = 0.90070, p-value = 0.0210). The dependent variable carbon emissions have a statistically significant and positive relationship with the impact of terrorism (LTEROR) and urban population (LTP), with coefficients of 0.049026 and 0.01611 and p-values of 0.018 and 0.025, respectively. These findings support the hypothesis that terrorism is a contributing factor to environmental degradation. Long-term environmental stress may result from population displacement, infrastructure construction, or disturbance of environmental management procedures.

The model is dynamically stable in the long run and supports the presence of a stable long-run equilibrium connection between the variables, as indicated by the short-run negative and significant coefficient of the error correction term (COINTEQ) (-0.18410, p-value = 0.0190). The GDP terms (DLGDP1 and DLGDP2) show how economic activity has a mixed effect on environmental deterioration, with significant changes being brought about by short-term volatility. The second GDP factor (DLGDP2) exhibits a sharply negative effect (coefficient = -23.65230, p-value = 0.0201), suggesting that the link is complicated and nonlinear, whereas a rise in GDP growth (DLGDP1) favorably affects CO₂ emissions (coefficient = 3.990931, p-value = 0.0295).

Short-term foreign direct investment (FDI) (DLFDI) has a negative but significant effect on environmental degradation (coefficient = -0.018205, p-value = 0.0124). This may indicate that FDI is channeled toward fewer polluting businesses or that short-term foreign investments do not immediately impair the environment. The short-term impact of the Climate Change Index (DLCCI) on CO₂ emissions is still positive and substantial (coefficient = 0.357511, p-value = 0.0108), which supports the idea that the region's environmental problems are exacerbated by the climate.

The data indicates that terrorism (DLTP) and the number of terrorist incidents

(DLTEROR) continue to have a significant impact on short-term environmental degradation (coefficients = 0.478802 and 0.143858, respectively). These findings underscore the ongoing and direct detrimental effects of terrorism on environmental health in South Asia. The relationship of variables such as FDI and Terrorism are in line with the findings of Bildirici and Gokmenoglu (2020) and Tahir et al. (2022). To summarize, the long- and short-term equations highlight the major effects of terrorism, climate change, economic expansion, and foreign direct investment on environmental degradation in South Asia. Because of the intricate relationships between these variables, it is suggested that in order to reduce environmental impact, sustainable development methods should take into account not just economic reasons but also security concerns, especially those related to terrorism.

Table 5 Pedroni Co integration Results

	Statistic	Prob.	Weighted Statistic
Panel v-Statistic	-2.132	0.016	-2.493
Panel rho-Statistic	2.753	0.009	3.133
Panel PP-Statistic	-2.307	0.010	-2.695
Panel ADF-Statistic	-2.234	0.012	-2.717
Alternative hypothesis: Individuals AR Coefs.(between-dimension)			
	Statistic	Prob.	
Group rho-Statistic	3.488	0.009	
Group PP-Statistic	-3.677	0.000	
Group ADF-Statistic	-3.575	0.000	

The above results show the panel cointegration test results in the context of investigating how terrorism affects environmental deterioration in South Asia. These tests assist in ascertaining whether a sustained correlation exists between the variables that are being studied, including terrorism (T), population, GDP per capita, FDI, environmental degradation (CO2 emissions), and climate change indices.

The Panel v-Statistic with the value of -2.132373 is negative and statistically significant with a probability of 0.0163, suggesting the rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration. This might be proof of a sustained correlation between the variables. Similarly, there appears to be some divergence from cointegration in the Panel Rho-Statistic, but it is still statistically significant with a positive value of 2.753018 and a probability of 0.0092. Both the Panel PP-Statistic and the Panel ADF-Statistic, with probability values of -2.307734 (p-value: 0.0105) and -2.234612 (p-value: 0.0127), respectively, are statistically significant and negative. Since they disprove the null hypothesis that there is no cointegration, these findings support the existence of a long-term equilibrium between the variables.

Additionally, the results of the between-dimension tests show that the Group PP-Statistic and Group ADF-Statistic are both negative and highly significant, with values of -3.677750 (p-value: 0.0001) and -3.575197 (p-value: 0.0002), respectively, and that the Group Rho-Statistic is positive (3.488757) and significant at the 0.0090 level. Together, these findings offer strong evidence that terrorism and environmental deterioration in South Asia have a long-standing, cointegrated link. The results of these experiments are significant because they show that, despite transient variations, factors like environmental deterioration and terrorism have a long-term, consistent

link.

Conclusion

This study explores the influence of Terrorism on Environmental Degradation in South Asian Region using a balance panel data for time period 2003-2021. The study faced unavailability of data for countries like Maldives, Bhutan and Afghanistan was missing so five countries were taken for examining relation between regressed and regressor. From the study we concluded that there is a strong, positive correlation over the long run between environmental degradation and terrorism implying that rising terrorism increases environmental damage. Early stages of expansion may make environmental problems worse since there is a positive correlation between economic growth and environmental impact. The link, however, becomes negative as economic development increases, indicating that while early economic growth may exacerbate environmental problems, these effects can be offset by later growth and greater foreign investment these results are consistent with the first and second stage of EKC respectively.

It is crucial to bolster border security, promote regional cooperation, and bolster law enforcement. More effective environmental governance will be possible with a more stable political and security landscape, which will lessen the destabilizing effects of terrorism on environmental policies. Environmental degradation is made worse by terrorism's propensity to cause pollution, displaced people, and the devastation of natural resources. Sustainability measures should be incorporated into national strategies to guarantee the protection of environmental resources even in times of war or instability. In the early phases of economic growth, in particular, policymakers should give priority to renewable energy, green technologies, and sustainable industrial practices. In addition to laying the groundwork for long-term improvements in environmental circumstances, this will assist in reducing the environmental harm brought on by rapid economic expansion. South Asian nations ought to welcome international investment, especially in fields that support renewable energy, environmentally friendly manufacturing processes, and sustainable agriculture. To guarantee that FDI is in line with environmental sustainability goals and does not lead to further environmental harm, robust regulatory frameworks must be established.

In order to combat environmental degradation, public involvement is essential. Governments should encourage communities to adopt sustainable practices and increase public understanding of the negative environmental effects of both economic activity and terrorism. Particularly in places impacted by terrorism, citizen empowerment initiatives such as education campaigns, community-based resource management, and grassroots environmental movements can enable residents to make a positive impact on environmental sustainability. These suggestions can help South Asian nations tackle the twin problems of environmental degradation and terrorism, paving the way for a more sustainable and safe future for the area.

The study has limitation on the unavailability of data for countries like Maldives, Bhutan, and Afghanistan.

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